

Influence of Application of e-Click-Based Information System and Role Obscurity on Work Satisfaction and Its Impact on Employee Performance Treasury Group PT. Bank XYZ

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ABSTRACT

Treasury Group plays a vital role in pursuing the ultimate goals of Bank XYZ programs and it has a great number of branch offices all around Indonesia, including in Medan. However, since 2014 it has been recorded that there is a decline in employee performance due to the lack of employee satisfaction at the workplace. The decreased work performance is marked by the falloff in transaction volume and fee-based income. Role obscurity is argued to be one of the main reasons for the poor work performance. In order to improve the level of work performance, Bank XYZ has shifted from conventional information system (paper-based) to e-click based system information. This has driven the researcher to conduct a research study aiming to investigate and analyze the influence of e-click based management system and the role obscurity on work performance and how it affects work satisfaction. 174 out of 232 employees of Treasury Group PT Bank XYZ. were chosen as participants using the random sampling technique. Data were collected using questionnaires and through observation and then were analyzed using path analysis and the sobel test. The results of the research revealed that: 1) the application of e-click based information system positively and significantly influences employee performance with employee satisfaction intervening, and 2) role obscurity negatively and significantly influences

employee performance with employee satisfaction intervening.

Keywords: Management Information Systems, Role Obscurity, Employee Satisfaction, Work Performance, Fee-Based Income

INTRODUCTION

Treasury plays a vital role for a bank, as does the heart for the human body. This department is responsible for managing and balancing daily financial movements and ensuring bank liquidity is maintained. Examples of liquidity are the availability of cash and non-cash customers. The department also handles investments in securities, foreign exchange trading and cash instruments. In addition, the Treasury is responsible for evaluating, securing and profitability of bank investment portfolios originating from excess funds not used for loan origination. Broadly speaking, Treasury is a cog as well as a risk management center for a bank.

The importance of quality human resources in the banking world, especially those working in the Treasury section, has become imperative. Given the competition in the banking industry even more when the challenges felt increasingly complex. The desire of banks to have a competitive advantage, requires them to always improve

the quality of their resources, while the quality of human resources is largely determined by the extent of the applicable system, able to support and satisfy the desires of employees of stakeholders in banking. Employee performance is the level of employee success in carrying out their duties and responsibilities Gibson, (2013: 165).

Employee performance in general is influenced by 2 factors, namely internal and external factors. Internal factors are factors that come from within the employee, which includes job satisfaction and things that can meet the needs of employees. Job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state in which employees view Handoko's work, (2011: 113). Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work that can be seen from the employee's attitude towards work and everything in his work environment. All types of companies actually need a work system that seriously considers the job satisfaction of its employees. Winidiantari P.N, and Widhiyani N.L.S (2015) suggested that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The productivity and efficiency of human resources is very dependent on a number of dynamic factors, ranging from personal factors to company policies. Job satisfaction is one of the most important factors affecting human resource productivity. For this reason, Ali and Wajidi (2013) state that ensuring employee job satisfaction is very important because employees are one of the main assets in the company where employees can be analogized as "fuel" that produces sustainable power.

Solanki (2013) suggested that job satisfaction and motivation are two of the important components in a person's professional life, as well as the main factors that influence the performance of the individual in the workplace. Job satisfaction affects the capability of employees both physically and mentally. Every individual needs to be physically and mentally healthy

in order to carry out their duties as best they can. In general, job satisfaction and motivation contribute to improving employee performance.

The role of employees in working becomes a certain indication of the formation of employee satisfaction. Employees always want clarity about the role that is accepted at work. However, the unclear role makes employees confused in completing their duties and responsibilities. In general the accepted concept of role ambiguity according to Lubis (2010: 58) states that ambiguity is the inadequacy of information held and the absence of clear directions and policies, uncertainty about authority, clear obligations and other relationships. Winidiantari P.N, and Widhiyani N.L.S (2015) in their research stated that the negative effect was not significant on performance. Whereas Wiguna, M (2014) provides different research results that role ambiguity has a negative and significant effect on performance.

Utilization of management information systems in companies or agencies is very important in supporting the day-to-day operations of the organization's management, which consists of information system resources to assist tactical planning and decision making, to support planning and policy formulation by management level. Winarno (2012: 149) explains that "Information systems are a collection of components that work together, which are used to record data, process data, and present information to decision makers in order to make decisions well. Management information systems are used to make employee work more effective and efficient. So that with the management system employees will not find it difficult and more advanced in the world of work. Sukarni and Askafi (2015) state that management information systems have a positive and significant effect on performance. However Zahari, (2017) states that management information systems have no significant positive effect on work efficiency.

PT Bank XYZ as one of Indonesia's banking institutions realizes that the future challenges to be faced will be even greater. Coupled with the condition of the banking sector in Indonesia is characterized by a weakening economic situation and increased financial market risk. This has an impact on the growth of the banking business in Indonesia which tends to slow down. With regard to these conditions, PT Bank XYZ needs to prepare superior and competitive human resources to improve company performance in the face of competition between banks and unfavorable business conditions.

PT Bank XYZ has many branches in Indonesia, including the treasury group. PT Bank XYZ always tries to serve the community optimally. The performance provided by Bank XYZ is always supported by the human resources that are in it. The duties and responsibilities of employees given by XYZ Bank have become SOPs that must be carried out and obeyed by employees.

One of the main benchmarks for employee performance at Bank XYZ Treasury Group is the achievement of targets on two important elements, namely Transaction Volume (denominated in dollars) and Fee-based Income (denominated in rupiah). An imbalance between the target value and the value achieved by employees from 2014 to 2018 both in transaction volume and fee-based income. In addition, the two graphs also show fluctuations in achievement figures from 2014 to 2018. Although there was an increase as in 2017, the surplus value achieved did not exceed the deficit value in previous years. Every year PT Bank XYZ has set a target number that must be achieved by the company. However, employees have not been able to reach the target, especially in 2018 where there is a difference between the target value and the realized value on transaction volume and fee-based income of more than 20%. This significant decrease was caused by employees who could not provide optimal

performance. One of the factors causing the decline in employee performance at Bank XYZ Treasury Group is the low level of employee dissatisfaction.

Additional tasks are jobs given by the leadership in the context of overtime work. However, employees feel a mismatch between the rewards received and the work given. This makes job satisfaction decrease, making employees often postpone work and cannot finish work on time. Employee satisfaction plays a role in employee life. Employee satisfaction at work makes employees more happy and enthusiastic in carrying out their duties. Employees who are not happy at work will be seen from the minimal level of attendance both at work and in participating in existing activities.

In addition to the reasons stated above, unclear roles are also indicated to be a cause of decreased employee performance. Based on the pre-survey conducted previously by the researcher. The results of the survey conducted on employees of Treasury Group XYZ consisting of 232 people show that there are still employees who give answers "no" for each statement point given with an average percentage of more than 40%. This can be interpreted that 40% of the total number of employees captures the existence of unclear roles within the Treasury Group XYZ.

Unclear roles or role conflicts become separate phenomena that need attention in the XYZ Treasury Group. Employees feel that there are inappropriate feelings and attitudes when carrying out their duties and responsibilities. There are employees who are given tasks by superiors to be done in a certain time such as doing tasks that are not actually their responsibility. Unclear role plays a role in looking at feelings of confusion and not hesitate to reject orders from superiors.

Employees who are given a burden by their superiors in doing their jobs feel uncomfortable because they know the conditions that occur in the field, namely the performance of fellow colleagues. However, due to the closeness of fellow employees,

other employees who were given the task were forced to give approval or approve of work reports that entered the supervisor's system. The existence of role conflicts that occur make employees often take advantage of the situation by establishing closer relationships with peers but with goals that are not in accordance with what is desired by the company.

In an effort to increase the work of Bank XYZ employees, since 2017 PT Bank XYZ has implemented an e-click system on every employee who has an NIP (employee identification number). The e-click system is used to make it easier for employees to carry out their duties and employees are expected to work into an archive that makes it easier for top management to see the work of employees. Management information systems play an important role in supporting the achievement of company goals, so we need an information system that is appropriate to the company's business processes and support from the company's human resources. The system development method commonly used in every bank is through the application of a new system to the organization carried out by coordinating service development activities.

Hypothesis

Based on the concept presented by the author, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

1. An e-click based management information system has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
2. Unclear role has a negative and significant effect on employee satisfaction in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
3. The e-click-based management information system has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
4. Unclear role has a negative and significant effect on employee performance in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
5. Employee satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
6. The management information system based on e-click has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through employee satisfaction in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
7. Unclear role has a negative and significant effect on

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study uses quantitative associative nature, namely research to examine the relationship / influence between variables. The population in this study are all employees in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ which are spread throughout Indonesia with a total of 232 employees. Sampling in this study was conducted using probability sampling techniques. According to Sugiyono (2010: 63), Probability sampling is a sampling technique that provides equal opportunities for each element (member) of the population to be elected as a sample member. The criteria used are random sampling and the calculation uses Slovin formula. So the numbers of samples in this study were 147 employees.

Data collection techniques in this study were carried out with a list of questions. Where this technique gives the responsibility to respondents to read and answer questions and researchers can provide an explanation of the purpose of the survey and questions that are less understood by respondents and responses to the questionnaire can be directly collected by researchers after being filled in by respondents. Questionnaires are personally used to obtain data about the dimensions of the constructs that are being developed in this study and Interviews, namely the process of obtaining information for research purposes by means of question and

answer. This interview was addressed directly to the employees of PT Bank XYZ.

Types and sources of data in this study are Primary Data and Secondary Data. Primary data are research data obtained directly from original sources (not through intermediary sources) and data collected specifically to answer research questions in accordance with the wishes of researchers (Indriatoro and Supomo (2012: 129) and Secondary Data, Secondary Data according to Indriatoro and Supomo (2012: 129), states that secondary data is data that is a source of research data obtained indirectly through intermediaries (obtained and recorded by other parties) Secondary data are generally in the form of evidence, notes, or historical reports that have been arranged in archive (documentary data) published and not published.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Management Information Systems Have a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Satisfaction

Application of management information systems (MIS) in an organization becomes an important basis in developing human resource capabilities. Today's SIM is inseparable from its role in the process of carrying out employee duties. SIM applications become very important which in one hand gives advantages that can help employees in completing their work, but on the other hand it will provide obstacles, especially for employees who do not master the application of information technology.

Information systems that are applied in organizations are components that are part of the organization together with individuals in the organization to interact with each other and use each other to get effective and efficient work. Management information system is a form of information system that functions to assist users in making decisions.

Measurement of a SIM application becomes a complex task because of the difficulty of tracing and measuring the

influence of a SIM, many measurements are used to measure the effect of an information system application, and none of the measurements is better than the others. Selection of measurements must consider several aspects, therefore researchers in the SIM field make measurements that represent SIM applications, for example: user information satisfaction, system usage and information value, et al., 2019; Lestari & Rini, 2020).

A system in XYZ Bank is basically divided into 2 groups. First, the system is seen from the emphasis on the elements or components of the system itself or commonly referred to as subsystems, and the second is more emphasis on interrelated procedures to achieve the goals to be achieved from the system created. Systems in the scope of information are considered as a set of components that work together to achieve goals or objectives. The main function of the system at XYZ Bank is receiving input, processing input, and producing output. In order to perform this function, the system will have components of input, process, output and control to ensure that all functions can run well. Components that are interconnected to collect and process.

Information systems for the purpose of assisting the planning, control, coordination and decision making of a work unit. Information becomes an important part in a work unit, because information plays a role in the progress and survival of the work unit. Information sourced from data that has been processed so that it can be a useful form for recipients of information. An information tries to provide an overview of events that occur at certain times, if related to the economic world, the events in the form of economic transactions aimed at decision making. Information is data that has been processed so that it can be used as consideration in decision making.

Integrated information is used as a useful input in the decision making process, because less time is needed to evaluate it, thereby increasing employee work

efficiency, so in this case information technology can have a positive impact on individual performance, the technology must be utilized and the technology must according to the type of work carried out by employees. This is the cause of employee satisfaction so it can be concluded that employees will feel satisfied if the work they do is in accordance with their expertise in the field of work.

This is in line with research conducted by Aji and Abdurachman (2011) which states that management information systems have a positive and significant effect on user satisfaction. Job satisfaction factors such as salary, training, promotion, work environment, actualization, and health to measure the level of individual performance, so it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between the quality of information system services to the satisfaction of its users, user satisfaction is considered as the user's response to the use of output information Systems. In addition, research conducted by Zahari, (2017) provides the same results that management information systems have a significant effect on satisfaction. Employees need a useful information system so that the presence of the system is expected to make employees more aware of their duties just by opening an employment link.

Unclear Roles Have a Negative and Significant Impact on Employee Satisfaction

Fanani, et al. (2008: 143) states that role conflict can occur when there are two different commands at the same time and between the two orders are contradictory. The role conflict can cause work quality to decrease because it is not followed by high concentration in carrying out the work. Other consequences that can be caused are work being uncomfortable, work tension and various other negative things that have an impact on the work results are not optimal. Role conflict is considered as a form of pressure from two different groups

so it is not possible to be able to obey all conflicting group rules.

Role conflict in this case is more considered as a form of conflict within the employee caused by different roles that must be played in sharing time. Role conflict occurs when an employee faces expectations that are not what was expected, so that what is expected is not created effectively. The decrease in employee satisfaction experienced by employees can also be caused by several factors, one of which is role ambiguity. Employees who experience role ambiguity will feel confused in carrying out their duties, this is because employees do not get clarity about information about their work. This if not addressed and continues to have a negative impact on physical, psychological and also employee behavior, such as the emergence of employees feeling dissatisfied with their work.

As is the case with PT Bank XYZ, indications of a decline in satisfaction are influenced by the unclear information and company procedures, which are caused by standardization and a standard system that is not in accordance with its application. So that many unclear procedures applied by the company. One of them is the procedure in the distribution of working hours is not in accordance with the existing contract. This causes the division of work hours of employees has not been done well, and some employees have not received the division of working hours in accordance with procedures.

In addition, employees often receive responsibility with incomplete instructions from superiors, which creates confusion for employees to carry out these tasks. The absence of clear job descriptions also causes employees to often perform tasks outside of responsibilities which can also interfere with employee concentration in carrying out their main tasks. This is in line with research conducted by Winidiantari P.N and Widhiyani N.L.S (2015) that role ambiguity has a negative effect on employee job satisfaction due to the absence of adequate

information needed by someone to carry out their role in a satisfactory way.

Unclear roles refer to the lack of clarity about job expectations, methods for meeting known expectations, and / or the consequences of a particular performance or role. Employees often have little information adequate to do their jobs or what they are responsible for in his role at the time. In addition, employees often work without much direction from supervisors and face new situations such as new clients, new industries, and new technical areas.

Individuals who experience unclear roles will experience anxiety, become more dissatisfied, and do work less effectively than other individuals thereby reducing their performance. Tang and Chang (2010) state that high role ambiguity can reduce a person's confidence in his ability to work effectively. The findings in this study support the results of Ramadan (2011), that a person can experience unclear roles if there is no clarity regarding work expectations due to lack of information for job completion or to explain the job and job descriptions.

Management Information Systems Have a Positive and Significant Effect on Performance

Management information systems have a significant role and benefits between data processing facilities and employees as users, where the relationship between one unit with another unit will be integrated in the process of data collection, data processing, data storage, data feedback, and data distribution to internal and external organization. The process of improving employee performance in one organization can be seen from the facilities that support employees in processing data in the form of information for the achievement of organizational goals.

Information systems will be needed as an organizational tool in conveying decisions that have been taken from the data that is processed. The information system used at XYZ Bank to process data is a

computer-based information system with a form of decentralized data processing. All data is inputted and processed based on the needs obtained and also carried out storage so that one day if the data is needed just open the data quickly.

Application of Management Information Systems (MIS) in organizations becomes an important basis in developing human resource capabilities. Today's SIM is inseparable from its role in the process of carrying out employee duties. SIM application becomes a double-edged knife, one side gives advantages that can help employees in completing their work, but on the other hand it will provide obstacles, especially for employees who do not master the application of information technology. Measurement of a SIM application becomes a complex task because of the difficulty of tracing and measuring the influence of a SIM, many measurements are used to measure the effect of an information system application, and none of the measurements is better than the others.

Selection of measurements must consider several aspects, therefore researchers in the SIM field make measurements that represent SIM applications, for example: user information satisfaction, system usage and information value. Employees are facilitated by computers so that office work can be completed effectively and easily in accessing information. In addition to employees, organizations must also realize that information is a fundamental need and is an important resource that must be managed properly. Thus, the existence of technology and information systems will facilitate in obtaining information and accelerate the organization in spreading information in order to avoid unexpected mistakes. Quality is part of every top management agenda. Quality targets are included in business plans.

The range of targets is derived from benchmarking, Targets are spread to the level that takes action, training is carried out at all levels, measurements are set entirely,

top managers regularly review progress against targets, awards are given for the best performance, reward systems are improved. This is in line with research conducted by Sukarni and Askafi (2015), as well as research conducted by Pamungkas, (2017) that management information systems have a positive and significant effect on performance.

The Unclear Role Has a Negative and Significant Impact on Performance

The role pressure that is often felt by employees is the lack of clarity when a person has unclear feelings about the information needed to complete the obligations of his job or does not get clarity about the job description and job obligations will be one of the factors that can reduce performance. When employees feel unclear about the work carried out it will have a negative impact on performance.

Good performance can be achieved with good quality human resources, with the help of an organizational structure that is able to reduce the workload and errors in work. Structure is a systematic approach step so that it is necessary to provide clear, structured tasks and procedures. Individual factors have a large role in influencing a person's performance as an individual or work in a team.

Unclear role is the inadequacy of information held and the absence of clear directions and policies, uncertainty of authority, obligations and relationships with others, and uncertainty of sanctions and rewards for behavior carried out. The unclear role that employees feel at XYZ Bank arises when the role expectations are not clearly understood and employees are uncertain about what needs to be done. Individuals experience unclear roles when they feel there is no clarity in their work expectations, such as lack of information needed to complete their work or not getting clarity about the job description of their work.

Someone can be said to be in a blurring of roles if he shows characteristics, among others, as follows Nimran, (2014: 101):

- a. It is unclear exactly what role is played.
- b. It is unclear to whom he is responsible and who reports to him.
- c. Not enough authority to carry out its responsibilities.
- d. Not enough to understand what was expected thereof.
- e. Do not understand the true role of the work in order to achieve overall goals.

If there is an unclear role or lack of acceptance by each member of the organization, then the leader should have to overcome it. Unclear roles require the ability and authority of leaders to explain the role of each member by reviewing tasks, delegating authority rights, obligations and responsibilities specified in the previous job description, which may require new adjustments according to the needs and abilities of members the.

Unclearness that is usually felt by employees is to do everything that is not their responsibility or perform tasks on the basis of an order from the leadership to help reduce their duties. However, if this continues to be done, the work of employees at the core of the description will be disrupted and make employee performance is not optimal. This is in line with research conducted by Wiguna, M (2014) and Winidiantari P.N, Widhiyani N.L.S (2015) which states that role ambiguity has a negative effect on employee performance.

Employee Satisfaction Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Performance

Employee performance is an important factor because the progress of an organization or company depends on the human resources they have. If performance increases, the success of achieving company goals is increasingly wide open, but if performance decreases it can result in setbacks for the company and the company cannot sustain its business. Seeing the increasingly tight competition and

development of the company, the company's performance is demanded not only to be maintained, but factors that need to be considered in an effort to improve the company's performance can also be an assessment of whether it will reduce the company's performance itself.

Human resources are an important factor determining the success of a company in achieving its goals, because the success or failure of a company in achieving its goals is very dependent on the ability of its human resources or employees in carrying out the tasks assigned. The ability of employees to carry out their duties can be seen through their performance, so that employee performance is very important for the success of the company. Employee performance is the output generated by the functions or dimensions of work or profession carried out by human resources or employees within a certain time (Wirawan, 2013: .732).

Good employee performance is characterized by the existence of good quality work in completing every job given by the leader in accordance with the specified time and can achieve every target set by the company, as stated by Mangkunegara (2013: 67) that performance is an achievement work or work results in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Every employee in a company needs to get satisfaction at work which can also have an impact on improving employee performance, because job satisfaction causes an increase in performance, so that satisfied workers will be more productive at work. Feelings of positive or negative attitudes towards work carry implications for themselves and the organization. If people are satisfied with their work, they like it and are motivated.

A number of factors which impact on the stability of the work of employees are often in the spotlight of companies and researchers. One of them is the achievement

of employee satisfaction which is an emotional condition that supports or does not work in an employee that is related to the employee's assessment of work or work experience. Employees who feel comfortable, valued, have the opportunity to develop themselves, will automatically focus attention and show good work performance on the work done (Dalimunthe, 2019; Ibrahim et al., 2020; Supriadi, Ritha F Dalimunthe. Priestin Lumbanraja, 2019) . This is in line with research conducted by Sukarni and Askafi (2015) stating that management information systems have a significant effect on performance.

Management Information Systems Have a Positive and Significant Effect on Performance through Employee Satisfaction

Management information systems are needed in the company. Where with the existence of a clear system and in accordance with procedures will help employees complete tasks quickly and make employees faster in knowing information that takes place in the company related to their work. This certainly will lead to employee satisfaction in knowing accurate information.

Every company makes information systems a staple for decision making. Information can fully support decision making if it takes place in a system. Organizational needs in information systems relate to the techniques of collecting, processing, storing, and easily rediscovering when needed and channeling information. An information system carries out all the transaction processing that is necessary for the organization and provides information and processing support for management functions including in terms of decision making.

An integrated information system is a system that connects front office and back office services in a single system. The benefits of an integrated system are lowering coordination costs, processing costs, processing time speed and accuracy

and reliability of data processed so that employees will become satisfied at work because the required data has been met and meets the concept of clarity.

An e-click based management information system at XYZ Bank is needed to input work reports and provide information on employee work. Like when doing overtime, working on holidays and reports on employee salaries accurately. With the management information system makes it easy for employees to access data without the need to distress other employee members because all the required data has been presented in the system.

The development of information technology in the modern era is now the right solution and cannot be dammed, in supporting decision making in an organization that allows jobs to be completed precisely, accurately, and efficiently. The development of information technology is so fast and the nuances of openness at this time required information so quickly supported by accurate facts and data.

As time is changing so fast, information technology has helped employees in their activities or organizations. Starting how to communicate, how to produce, how to coordinate, how to think, and how to make decisions through the use of information technology in various activities. Management information system is the right management in an effort to carry out work quickly, precisely, and organized. Not only that management information systems can be used as material for planning, decision making and evaluation. Management information systems are generally intended to produce information in all fields including finance, personnel and so on all related to organizational activities are tactical so that in this case the management information system can improve employee performance.

In addition to supporting the process of decision making, coordination, and supervision, information systems can also

help managers and employees analyze problems, describe complex things, and create new products. This is in line with research conducted by Sukarni, Askafi (2015) and Pamungkas, (2017) that management information systems have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Unclear Roles Have a Negative and Significant Effect on Performance through Employee Satisfaction

Human resources are a very important factor in an organization, both large and small scale organizations. Quality human resources have a role in improving organizational performance. If HR is not qualified and not managed properly, especially if there is often unclear roles or role ambiguity will affect employee performance. An employee needs conducive working conditions to help expedite the process of achieving the goals of the organization or company.

Working conditions serve as a means to direct or regulate good activities so that leaders and employees can work calmly, comfortably, so that productivity will be controlled in accordance with what is desired by the organization or company. The effectiveness of a working condition is determined by how far the working conditions are in accordance with the resources and the environment. More specifically, it can be said that high role uncertainty (role ambiguity) will reduce job satisfaction. The characteristics of unclear roles perceived by employees are as follows:

1. Do not know clearly what the purpose of the role it plays.
2. It is not clear to whom he is responsible and who reports to him.
3. Not enough authority to carry out their responsibilities.
4. Not fully understanding what is expected of him.
5. Not properly understanding the role of his work in order to achieve overall goals.

The unclear role of employees is felt at Bank XYZ because they do not have enough information to be able to carry out their duties, or do not understand or realize the expectations associated with a particular role. In short, people who experience unclear roles are when they don't know what is expected of them. Newcomers to the company often complain about poor job descriptions and promotion criteria. Meanwhile, according to Kreitner and Kinicki (2014: 17), prolonged unclear confusion can cause the following things:

1. Dissatisfaction with work
2. Scrape confidence
3. Inhibit job performance

Role conflict occurs because workers have norms and value systems that they obtain in the process of activities that conflict with the norms, rules and value systems that apply in the company. Role balance is important to be studied more deeply because it will have an impact on employee performance. This is in line with research conducted by Wiguna, M (2014) that role ambiguity has a negative effect on performance. And research conducted by Winidiantari P.N, and Widhiyani N.L.S (2015) that role ambiguity has a negative effect on satisfaction and performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions in this study are:

1. An e-click based management information system has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
2. Unclear role has a negative and significant effect on employee satisfaction in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
3. The e-click-based management information system has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.

4. Unclear role has a negative and significant effect on employee performance in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
5. Employee satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
6. The management information system based on e-click has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through employee satisfaction in the Treasury Group of PT Bank XYZ.
7. Unclear role has a negative and significant effect on employee performance through employee satisfaction at Treasury Group Bank XYZ.

Recommendations

The suggestions in this study are:

1. The average respondent answers disagree with the statement that the system being run provides functions that are useful for employees. Not all employees understand the main function of XYZ Bank's e-click management information system. In this case, the implementation of information systems in the company is still not optimal, especially in maximizing the use of data available in the information system for decision making. For this reason, it is necessary to hold a seminar or workshop to discuss the functions of the XYZ Bank management information system in detail and this seminar must be attended by all elements in the XYZ Bank Treasury. XYZ Bank must ensure that employees understand and know the e-click-based SIM function.
2. The average respondent stated disagree with the statement that employees have clarity in the right to approve decisions related to certain policies. Bank XYZ should review policies that may be related to the work of employees. By utilizing the existing e-click based SIM, complicated bureaucracy should be cut.

3. The average employee states not agree with the statement that the employee has a clear responsibility. Top management of Treasury Bank XYZ needs to sit down with subordinates to discuss matters relating to rights, authority and responsibilities. This meeting should be held regularly so that problems that will arise in the future can be handled early. In addition, the following two important components need to be explained in the job description: main task and additional tasks.
4. On average, employees answered that they did not agree with the questionnaire statement that employees had the opportunity to raise positions periodically. Top management of Treasury Bank XYZ should investigate whether employee assumptions regarding job appraisal that are one of the prerequisites for promotion are still subjective. There needs to be transparency in how this work assessment is carried out. SIM can be used as a platform to display employee performance development and performance development charts must be visible to all employees to motivate employees to work harder. In addition, researchers who are also one of the XYZ Treasury Bank employees hope that superiors will provide more positive reinforcement in the work environment.
5. On average, employees answered that they did not agree with the questionnaire statement that Bank XYZ paid attention to the psychological condition of the employees. This certainly can be one of the benchmarks of how much the level of employee job satisfaction. Employees are assets for the company. Without employees, the wheels of business turnover will not run. For this reason, researchers hope that Bank XYZ will pay more attention to the psychological condition of its employees. Competitive bonuses as well as opportunities for promotion are not the only factors that determine employee job satisfaction. Employees need to be given more space to refill their enthusiasm and motivation at work. If necessary, involve professionals such as psychologists to see the extent to which stress caused by high employee workload can affect employee performance.
6. The average employee states that he disagrees with the questionnaire statement that superiors act responsively in making decisions concerning employees. Good two-way communication between superiors and subordinates in an organization is the key to an excellent and pleasant management system. For this reason, top management of Treasury Bank XYZ needs to open communication channels with employees to discuss urgent matters, especially those concerning work and staffing. Bosses need to prioritize problems faced by employees to be resolved immediately.
7. One of the dimensions of management information systems is management itself. Superior management information systems without good governance will not make it easy for users. For this reason, efficiency becomes an important point that must be considered when a company decides to integrate technology in its work system. In this case, Treasury Bank XYZ has a good management information system. However, with the existence of an e-click-based management information system, work procedures are still the same. Employees assess the complicated bureaucratic pruning at XYZ Treasury Bank did not occur. Employees still have to go through a long bureaucracy. What's different is that the procedure is no longer done on paper, but through online media. For example, the submission of employee overtime realization must still go through three stages. The first stage, employees must input work plans then wait for approval from superiors. Second, employees must input overtime plans and then wait for approval from

the supervisor. Finally, employees must submit realization of overtime and wait for approval from superiors. There are several weaknesses in this procedure. One of the weaknesses that is considered the most detrimental to employees is that employees must submit an overtime plan at the beginning of the month. In practice, employees often get assignments that should be counted overtime but these tasks have not been included in the proposed overtime plan. This condition often results in XYZ Treasury Bank employees not satisfied with the existing work system because employees do not get paid overtime as they should. For this reason, researchers suggest that the XYZ Treasury Bank be able to review existing procedures and maximize the use of an e-click-based SIM. An e-click based SIM should be able to be utilized as a data and information center so that long and complicated procedures can be simplified. For example, in the submission of overtime realization, the first and second stages should not be needed. All data regarding work plans and employee overtime should have been recorded on an e-click-based SIM and the employee only needs to check the list and report on the tasks that have been carried out including explaining additional tasks that have not been included in the realization of overtime submitted at the beginning of the month.

8. One form of unclear role that occurs within the Treasury Bank XYZ is that there are employees who have access to a boss's e-click based SIM account. This situation is often used by some elements to commit fraud. The fraud in question is that employees who are close to employees who have "privileges" can easily get approval for things that benefit the requestor without the boss knowing. An example is the realization of overtime. To that end, researchers offer a solution so that Treasury Bank XYZ can act decisively by blocking the

way for all forms of fraud. Treasury Bank XYZ can consider to complement the security information management system based on e-click with finger scan or face ID. With this feature, only employers can approve and input data.

9. The provision of appropriate overtime salaries is one of the supports to job satisfaction of XYZ Treasury Bank employees which has a positive impact on their performance. In this case, Treasury Bank XYZ has provided competitive overtime salaries. However, there are still errors in the calculation of overtime salaries. Officers who calculate employee overtime salaries must ensure compatibility between the data on the finger print and the XYZ Bank SIM user. This is very possible because the finger print machines at XYZ Bank use intranet networks with IP addresses connected to the XYZ Bank IT team.
10. This research is expected to be used as a reference for further research relating to concepts or theories that support knowledge of human resource management and it is hoped that the next researcher can consider the use of other variables such as workload, leadership, appreciation, job description, quality of sources human power and others.

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